

PRODUCTION ACTIVITIES OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

Saidmuradova T. S.

Senior lecturer

Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry.

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Annotation. *This article presents the main target indicators of the development of the processing chain in the sewing and knitting industry, the volume of production of spinning and textile enterprises, the dynamics of the production of ready-made sewing and knitting products in comparison with previous years, and today's export activity of textile industry enterprises of our Republic, as well as the main aspects of the relationship between foreign trade and textile products in the development of the textile industry.*

Key words: *textile industry, sewing and knitting industry, processing, competitiveness, export, export geography, import, comparative analysis, private entrepreneur, statistical agency, production dynamics, foreign trade activity, diversification.*

Today, broad conditions are being created to further increase the investment attractiveness and competitiveness of the textile and garment and knitwear industry, expand the export potential of the sector, and facilitate the wider penetration of local textile products into foreign markets.

In particular, comprehensive measures are being implemented to develop the textile and garment and knitwear sectors of light industry, expand the types and assortment of finished products produced and sales markets, as well as comprehensively support the investment and export activities of enterprises in the sector [4].

In this regard, on January 16, 2025, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6 "On additional measures to develop the processing chain in the textile and garment and knitwear industry" was issued. According to this Decree, the main target indicators for the development of the processing chain in the textile and garment and knitwear industry in 2025-2027 are:

- to increase exports of products to 4.0 billion US dollars in 2025, 5.0 billion US dollars in 2026, and 7.0 billion US dollars in 2027;
- to increase exports of finished products to the markets of the United States and European countries to 500 million US dollars;
- to increase the share of finished sewing and knitting products in total exports to 70 percent through the widespread introduction of advanced technologies and modern design developments and the attraction of international brands;
- to attract foreign investments and loans in the amount of 5.0 billion US dollars in order to further develop deep processing of yarn and thread [1].

All measures aimed at developing the textile industry are contributing to increasing the economic efficiency of enterprises and the production of competitive products.

Today, the Republic is implementing a comprehensive set of measures aimed at organizing the production of a wide range of high-quality textile and garment and knitwear products, deepening the localization of their production, as well as increasing the export potential of local manufacturers.

The necessary legal framework and favorable conditions for the development of the textile and garment and knitwear industry have been formed, and a number of Presidential and Government resolutions have been adopted aimed at deepening reforms in the sector.

The textile industry is widespread in all our regions and is a potential industrial sector that employs the largest number of people. Today, more than 7 thousand enterprises operate in the sector, employing 570 thousand people. Of these, more than 2 thousand enterprises operate within the framework of the “Uztukimachiliksanoat” association, employing 365 thousand people.

The export potential of the sector has doubled in the last 3 years. Last year, this figure amounted to \$ 1.6 billion. At the same time, the sector has sufficient reserves and opportunities. In particular, there is an opportunity to fully process the cotton grown in our country, bringing exports to \$ 15 billion and providing employment to more than 3 million people.

The most important direction of our domestic reserves and capabilities has been the gradual increase in the level of processing of local raw materials, as well as the expansion of the volume and types of production of high value-added products. Over the past 31 years, the industry has become one of the leaders both in attracting foreign investment and in the export of high value-added products. Today, light industry is represented by a wide export range, including all types of products, from yarn to finished sewing and knitted products.

If we look at the structure of light industry, we can observe that the production and export of these sectors are growing. In 2021, the enterprises of the sector exported goods worth 1.9 billion US dollars to the world market.

According to the Statistics Agency, textile products worth 89.5 trillion soums were produced in 2024. This figure increased by 11.1% compared to the same period in 2023, and the volume of textile products produced accounted for 10.1% of total industrial production [2].

Textile products produced in our country are exported to the CIS countries, European and Turkish countries, South and East Asian countries, the Middle East and African countries, and the geography of exports is expanding year by year.

Today, the textile industry exports of our Republic amounted to about 2.9 billion US dollars in January-December 2024. Including:

- Yarn - 1,237.3 million dollars,
- Finished textile products - 1,124.5 million dollars
- Knitted fabrics - 292.1 million dollars
- Woven fabrics - 145.9 million dollars
- Hoodies - 42.6 million dollars.

This accounted for 10.6 percent of the total export volume [2].

Today, China, India, Turkey, Pakistan, developing countries of Southeast Asia and Latin America are among the main competitors of Uzbekistan in the textile market. It is known that the availability of raw material reserves (mainly cotton fiber), low cost of energy carriers and availability of qualified and relatively cheap labor force are the specific advantages of our country's manufacturers [3].

To achieve the set results, the “Uztukimachiliksanoat” Association, in cooperation with international organizations and industrial enterprises, is developing a strategy for exporting textile products to the European Union market.

Foreign trade activity plays an important role in the development of the textile industry of Uzbekistan.

The main aspects of the relationship between foreign trade and textile products of Uzbekistan are: textile exports, large volumes of exports, competitiveness, diversification of trade markets, imports of textile materials and equipment.

Foreign trade plays an important role in the development of the textile industry of Uzbekistan, providing export opportunities, attracting investment and technology, as well as business relations with partners around the world. This contributes to the development of the sector, the creation of new jobs, and an increase in the country's income.

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 16, 2025 No. PF-6 “On additional measures to develop the processing chain in the textile and garment knitwear industry”.
2. STATISTICS / Official channel.
3. Data from the “Uztukimachilik sanoati” association.